

Project¹ Number: 101113522

Project Acronym: POLIRNA

Project title: Kits for advanced polymer-lipid nanocarriers for targeted delivery of RNAs to cardiac and skeletal muscle cells

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

¹ The term ‘project’ used in this template equates to an ‘action’ in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation

1. Data Summary

The main aim of POLIRNA is the design and validation of advanced kits for the preparation of ligand-functionalized polymer-lipid nanocarriers able to release non-coding RNAs (e.g., miRNAs and siRNAs) to target cells, i.e. cardiomyocytes and skeletal muscle cells for preclinical research studies. POLIRNA will exploit the versatility and user-friendliness of a patented method developed in the ERC funded project BIORECAR (772168).

To achieve this aim different tasks will be pursued, comparing data of POLIRNA nanocarriers with control transfection lipidic reagents and clinically approved lipid nanoparticles:

(i) **The design of kits**, by the definition of kit materials, sterilization conditions, preparation protocols, and the conditions for nanocarrier storage after preparation. The physicochemical properties of ligand-functionalized nanocarriers to target cardiomyocytes and skeletal muscle cells will be assessed.

(ii) ***In vitro* validation of nanocarriers** prepared from kits, using target cells, by evaluating dose-dependent cell viability/cytotoxicity, hemolysis, miRNA/siRNA cell uptake, transfection efficiency and their dependence on nanocarrier surface functionalization degree.

(iii) ***In vivo* biodistribution of nanocarriers** prepared from kits in mouse models.

To this aim, existing data such as experimental protocols from scientific literature and BIORECAR previous work will be adapted and optimized to fit the needs of the project. Data obtained from POLIRNA will be exploited for the filing of a new patent, for the publication and dissemination of non-IP sensitive results by scientific articles and conference presentations, and to support the foundation of a spin-off company. To these aims, the newly generated data from each experiment will be collected, saved in proper folders in personal laptops/computers, external drives and in clouds (e.g., OneDrive and Dropbox) and, once the datasets are complete, they will be uploaded into a data repository platform (e.g., Zenodo, protected under CC-by-NC license). Considering the aim to found a started up company (indeed already achieved on February 2024, month 5 of the project) and to file new patents, only non-IP sensitive data will be shared with the scientific community.

During the project, several types and formats of data will be generated, including:

- digital numerical data, collected from experimental measurements into specific file formats (e.g.: “.skax” for ThermoFisher™ Varioskan™ LUX plate reader files) and exported for elaboration in Excel (.xlsx) and GraphPad (.pzfx) files.
- images of samples collected under microscope format (.nd2) and exported into .jpeg, .png or .tiff formats.
- experimental protocols and reports in .pdf, .doc and .ppt files.

Files of each experiment will be named accordingly as: name of the experiment _ condition tested _ operator’s initials _ day-month-year) and saved within dedicated folders for each characterization type (named as “Characterization_NP type”) into POLIRNA folder both into personal computers/laptops protected by a password (belonging to the PI and POLIRNA staff) and into OneDrive Cloud. Moreover, POLIRNA research output (data, software, posters, presentations, deliverables, etc.) will be deposited in a trusted depository (e.g., Zenodo and, if possible, into the new EU Open Research Repository).

Collected experimental data (e.g., quantitative measurements of cell cytocompatibility at different nanocarrier concentrations), optimized methods and adapted protocols from literature

will be converted into a suitable format for publication purposes during the preparation of the manuscripts and abstracts/presentations for congresses. In the early project phase, all data generated, if not published or patented yet, will serve as a database for internal use within the Host Institution research group.

During the project, the generated data will be exploited for patent filing, publications (scientific articles) and other forms of dissemination (*i.e.*, poster and oral presentations at conferences), as well as the participation to outreach events (*e.g.*, Just the Woman I am event organized in Turin every year at the beginning of March; Pint of Science in Turin on May 13, 2024; the EU Researchers' Night, etc.). A patent anteriority search will be first performed to assess the possibility of patent filing, before sharing any crucial information. Scientific publications of non-IP sensitive data will be made available open access (OA). Research data from each published paper will be stored in an open data repository (*e.g.*, Zenodo). By the end of the project, also unpublished research data will be stored in the open data repository.

During the project, data from the scientific literature and/or repositories (*e.g.*, experimental protocols) will be re-used upon proper source citation and permission from copyright owners in case of non-open access data. Specifically, the protocol for nanocarrier preparation, previously patented in BIORECAR ERC project, will be adapted and optimized for further applications in POLIRNA. Existing protocols for *in vitro* and *in vivo* validation of nanocarriers will be also re-used, by citing previous publications and/or datasets in repositories, while highlighting any implemented modification. Available experimental data from literature will serve for comparison during the experimental work, enabling validation of results, obtained under the same experimental conditions.

2. FAIR data

2. 1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The team will store all generated data into a free and trusted repository (*e.g.*, Zenodo and, if possible, into the new EU Open Research Repository for which we sent the request to be added in the pilot launch). Therefore a DOI will be generated for each stored data, as an a unique and standard identification code making them findable for further re-use under proper source citation.

Stored data files such as experimental protocols (.pdf), collected data from experiments (.xlxs), and images (.jpeg, .png or .tiff), will be named according to the sample and experiment type, date of the experiment and researcher's initials (*e.g.*, "CHP uptake_01012024_VC"). A version number will be also added at the end in the file name starting from 1 (*e.g.*, "CHP uptake_01012024_VC_v1") to separately collect any further data update. This will ensure that all stored data are findable through sample type, the experiment performed, its date and the operators' name and its repetition.

The deposited data will be provided with their own metadata which includes:

- file name
- short description
- keywords
- DOI
- date of creation
- version number
- size of the file

- creator/ownership
- modification abilities/data protection

2.2. Making data openly accessible

By the end of the first year, the team will store data (*e.g.*, deliverables, milestones, posters submitted to conferences and outreach events, etc.) in Zenodo depository (with monthly updates). IP-sensitive data will be protected under an embargo. Since the generated data from experimental work (excel files with raw and processed data, experimental protocols and images, etc.) are not only mostly IP-sensitive but also ‘living data’, as soon as new versions of the data (*i.e.*, modified protocols) will be obtained during the course of the project, they will be stored under embargo protection. After a careful analysis of patenting opportunities, data that cannot be patented will be used for open access (OA) publications and for other types of disseminations. Once these data have been published in OA scientific articles, I will change the protection of these data in Zenodo and make them accessible. Data not used in publications or patents, will be made OA available after 12 months from the end of the project

The data will be provided in an accessible way and I will ensure that they are readable through widely available or free softwares (*i.e.*, Excel, Acrobat Reader, ImageJ, Power Point or Word files). In case that any specific software is needed to open some of the shared data, the type of software will be clearly indicated and instructions for opening and treating the files will be provided.

Data, as well as the associated metadata and the needed documentation/instructions, will be stored into Zenodo, a certified and trusted data depository available for free. Zenodo repository have the possibility to store any type of data (up to 50 GB per file) with a large choice of privacy content (upon online free registration). Options to choose the access to the stored data from open to embargoed and updates of the deposited data can be done at any time, as well as changes in privacy content. Zenodo repository can be used as a personal repository (for data storage under embargo), and as a platform for data sharing, as it offers the possibility to generate a DOI to the stored data, thus making them available and sharable with external users. Zenodo is an online free depository and did not present any restrictions on use. The repository is accessible even without proper authentication. Registration and free account creation is mandatory for the storage of data. Zenodo is hosted at the CERN and managed by several highly-qualified staff members ensuring the storage and the security of the stored data under strict rules. Data that are not appropriate or with missing metadata information can be removed from the depository as out of the scope leading to a DOI revocation. Zenodo depository is accessible online through any computer or device equipped with a screen and internet connection. All external users can have access to the files in Zenodo repository without proper online identification (only for OA content). Since POLIRNA project is at his early stage, and some data may be used for patenting reasons, I will ensure the full OA to stored data only after a careful analysis of patenting opportunities.

2.3. Making data interoperable

One of the aims of the project is to collect data for comparison with results already available in the literature, meaning the comparison of POLIRNA nanocarrier with control transfection reagents (LipofectamineTM and DharmaFECT®) and clinically approved LNPs (with OnpatroTM composition) creating thus a wider database in the field. To do so, the data will be collected in the same format as the one in which they have been already published (*e.g.*, PDF

reports or articles). Additionally, most relevant data for comparison reasons will be organized in Excel files (including a first sheet with all the relevant information and instructions; relevant data will be collected in different sheets depending on the type of characterization, facilitating consulting and reuse). Experimental protocols will be provided in PDF format.

I will make sure that all team members will employ the same vocabulary, keywords and annotations already used within the scientific community in the field and defined in literature, to ensure the interoperability of data generated in the project. In case of any deviations, in the first description sheet, a list of abbreviations and definitions, relevant information, and the vocabulary employed for data will be provided.

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

Non-IP sensitive data will be made available after manuscript publication with no embargo and will be licensed through CC-by-NC license, ensuring thus their re-use (through Zenodo repositories). The produced data could be re-used for non-commercial reasons by third parties, under proper citation of the used data (through the DOI generated in Zenodo repositories).

All POLIRNA generated data will be stored with embargo into Zenodo repository and updated within the course of the project as they are “living data”. IP-sensitive data will remain protected under embargo for patenting reasons. Non-IP sensitive data used for publications purposes will be made permanently OA after the publication date. Other non-IP and non-published data will be made available OA by the end of the project, generally within 1 year from the end of POLIRNA project or in any case no later than 3 years from the project end (in case of late publications).

Once the stored data are made available OA, they will be ready to use by third parties upon adequate citation source (*i.e.*, DOI). Since I will provide a permanent OA to the stored data by the end of the project (except for those selected as IP-sensitive data), data will be usable after the end of the project (upon proper source citation).

Moreover, since generated and stored data are “living data”, during their lifecycle some of them may become obsolete or irrelevant, following the evolution of the project. Thus, by updating new versions of the data, changes in data removal or cleaning will be clearly highlighted by providing clear explanation (e.g., in a separate excel sheet, or by adding comments or footnotes on PDF documents). In this way, data quality assurance process can be easily followed by anyone who is interested in re-using the data (once OA available).

3. Allocation of resources

In this early project phase, there are no costs related to project data management (since no big amount of data have been generated yet). As soon as data are stored, POLIRNA team will use free repositories, such as Zenodo. Data files will be prepared by all researchers involved in POLIRNA project and checked by me. Free clouds (*e.g.*, Dropbox or OneDrive) will be used to store data, together with personal laptops or computers, as well as external storage units (*e.g.*: hard disks). Hence, I do not foresee costs for data management, except for the acquisition of external hard disks and computers. In case of changes, I will update this plan accordingly.

In the event that management and storage of POLIRNA data require additional costs, they will be covered through the budget allocated to the project, as a part of project management (corresponding to WP4). In the second half of the project, I will plan resources for long-term data preservation, if needed.

4. Data security

Currently, data are stored in laptops and computers protected by a password, and a version is also stored in POLIRNA folder in clouds (*i.e.*, OneDrive and Dropbox). An external hard disk (of few TB capacity) is also used to save all data. For long-term preservation of data, a trusted repository, such as Zenodo, is going to be used to upload the first data (scientific deliverables and milestones). Since the project is at the beginning these early data will be protected under an embargo to allow new patent submission.

5. Ethical aspects

Authorization for animal tests will be also collected from subcontractors and stored in POLIRNA folder in OneDrive cloud, shared within POLIRNA team, as well as in Zenodo and kept under embargo as IP-sensitive data concerning nanoparticle preparation are included.

6. Other issues

My data management plan includes the storage of data in the institutional server provided by Politecnico di Torino. I will follow any new instructions from my institution.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	07.05.2024	▪ Initial version_Month 6